

**The Third MSSRF South - South Exchange
Travelling Workshop: 15-22 October
2004 Tamil Nadu & Pondicherry, India**

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The Third MSSRF South - South Exchange Travelling Workshop

15-22 October 2004
Tamil Nadu & Pondicherry, India

Workshop Report

M S SWAMINATHAN RESEARCH FOUNDATION

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Foreword

The past decade has witnessed the rise of ICT-enabled development initiatives, notably the emergence of information kiosks (or telecentres) in different parts of the developing world. Concurrently, there has also been an increase in the number of skeptics who question the wisdom of investing in 'ICT4D' programmes when there are more serious concerns such as widespread hunger, poverty, malnutrition, and illiteracy. While many ICT4D experiments failed to deliver, no doubt there have been some successful experiments to show that ICTs, if used intelligently and innovatively and are embedded in a holistic development strategy, can make a difference. But these experiments are yet to be scaled up. Incidentally, MSSRF has formed a National Alliance to upscale the IDRC-supported Information Village Research Project, which operates in a dozen villages in Pondicherry, into a nationwide endeavour of making every village a knowledge centre.

How can we replicate such successful programmes? One way is to bring together development activists from many countries and facilitate sharing knowledge and experience. That is precisely what we at MSSRF have been doing in the past three years. Every year, we invite about 20 development workers – both from NGOs and from other agencies – to spend eight days with us, travelling from village to village, visiting knowledge centers and other development projects of MSSRF, meeting the volunteers and the local communities and learning from one another and sharing experiences. In addition to replicating what is done in India, the workshops allow for cross-fertilization with similar experiences elsewhere so that what is being done in similar situations can be shared, learnt and adopted where appropriate. I see these workshops as informal classrooms and knowledge is shared both by the villagers and the visitors.

The first such workshop took place in 2002 with support from Hivos, IICD and IDRC. The second workshop was held in 2003 with financial and logistic support from GKP. The third workshop held in October 2004 was also fully supported by GKP.

We invited Robert Chapman of ODI, London, and Geeta Sharma of OneWorld South Asia, New Delhi, to join the workshop as participants and prepare a report. In his report Robert concentrates on MSSRF's work and philosophy and emphasizes rightly that at MSSRF ICTs are not seen as a technical solution on their own but as enablers in a process of local prioritization and problem solving. He relates the success of the programme to embedding ICTs in a holistic approach encompassing a diverse range of development initiatives. Geeta, on the other hand, provides a narrative of events that took place and ends her report with quotes from the participants and a few suggestions.

We are grateful to all the participants, Robert and Geeta. We hope they found the workshop a rewarding experience. We are happy that many members of the GKP Secretariat, Richard Gerster, Geraldine Kouadio and Kathryn Johnson could join us on the first three days. But they missed the inauguration of the ISRO-MSSRF Village Resource Centres by India's Prime Minister through satellite-enabled video conferencing which took place on the fourth day. We are grateful to the village communities and volunteers in Pondicherry, Thiruvaiyaru and Dindigul district for their hospitality and enthusiastic participation in the workshop. We are grateful to our partner organizations – Rajiv Gandhi Veterinary College, Aravind Eye Hospitals, SEVA, DHAN Foundation – for welcoming the participants and telling them about their philosophy and work. We are grateful to GKP for supporting the event two years in a row. We consider the workshop as part of our contribution to GKP and we are looking for other ways to contribute. We are grateful to IDRC and CIDA for their support of the Information Village Research Project in Pondicherry, and to the scientists of the J R D Tata Ecotechnology Centre of MSSRF, who run the Biovillage Project.

On the last day of the workshop we asked participants to come up with one word that was upper most in their minds that would sum up their response to the workshop. Sunith from Thai Rural Net, the youngest member in the group, came up with 'Hope'. I felt very happy. It meant the workshop was a great success.

I am looking forward to the next workshop and to sharing knowledge and experience with a new set of partners. I guess if you enjoy doing something, it becomes an addiction!

Happy reading! And your comments are welcome.

March 2005

S. Arunachalam

Arun

(Subbiah Arunachalam)

Distinguished Fellow, MSSRF

and five from GKP Secretariat) who took part in the Pondicherry leg of the workshop – the first three days. This report outlines the MSSRF approach to establishing ICT-enabled knowledge centres and this experience of learning in the global village.

Figure 1: The hub and spokes model in Pondicherry

1. The MSSRF hub and spokes model

The hub and spokes model is innovative in two ways. First, the model is technologically innovative using the latest information and communication technologies (ICTs) to connect villages together and to the wider information networks of the outside world. Second and perhaps more importantly the institutional structure of the model is innovative in the way it is designed to *'reach the unreachable'*.

Figure 2: Institutional structure for Pondicherry knowledge centres

empowered by having a new role of assisting community members access useful information. The volunteers also have greater voice in community affairs and have established enterprises together as self help groups.

The village committee for the knowledge centre is in charge of providing suitable and well maintained premises for the knowledge centre. In villages such as Embalam the trustees of the local temple have taken on this role and in all cases the community has provided premises that is open for everyone to access.

Local content creation

Local language databases on topics such as government services, agriculture and education have been systematically created since the project was initiated in 1998. Although the hub staff have access to the Internet most of the database content has been created specifically from local information sources

communities to use the knowledge centres as a catalyst for capacity building and income generating livelihood diversification.

Embalam	Farming, livestock, SHGs purchased power tiller to rent out to farmers, micro-enterprise production of shell crafts, incense sticks, soaps	Computer training, SHG accounting software, web cam for eye tests with Aravind Eye hospital, livestock information kiosk (developed by Rajiv Gandhi Veterinary College) with local language and touch screen application. Farmers access daily prices for produce on the local market.
Pillayarkuppam	Horticulture, floriculture, mushrooms, biopesticides, fish, ducks, vermicompost	SHG accounting software, computer training, coordination of biovillage training sessions and demonstrations.
Kunichampet	SHGs producing herbal medicine	Children and youth computer training, job searching and eye testing.
Kalitheerthalkuppam	Farming and milk production. Local milk co-operative encouraged by knowledge centre to install a computer for daily record keeping	Farmers access information on biopesticide and fertiliser prices, weather information at time of rice harvesting, daily vegetable market prices. Child health information and computer assisted learning program for children.
Sempatti	Farming, horticulture, floriculture	Satellite-based video conferencing between villager and experts in remote locations. Computer-aided learning programme for tribal children.

State Bank of India. The SHGs are trained to use local language accounting software to manage the business planning for their enterprise and loan repayment. The government of Pondicherry has asked MSSRF to establish a further 256 biovillages as part of a five year plan. Many women are only employed as wage labourers for 70 days a year and therefore these enterprises offer them a chance to supplement their income significantly for the rest of the year.

In K. Ramanathapuram village in Dindigul district a self help group consisting of 12 women has started to produce a biopesticide to control seed borne pathogens. MSSRF arranged for two members of the group to spend a week on a special course in Tamil at the Department of Plant Pathology of the Tamil Nadu Agricultural University in Coimbatore. The SHG is now producing the biopesticide *Pseudomonas fluorescens* for sale to local farmers and companies further afield in Trichy and Chennai. In Sevanakarayanpatty village the Jansirani SHG is producing paper and board from banana

Thai Ruralnet, Thailand.	Promoting the use of ICTs in support of rural development in Thailand. Empowering rural communities to use more traditional approaches to land husbandry.	Databases of indigenous knowledge collected. Youth groups mobilised as social entrepreneurs using ICT in rural areas.
Centre for Environment Education, (CEE) Gujarat, India.	Environmental awareness raising through innovative programmes and educational material for training and dissemination for children and youth.	Multi media materials, library and documentation centre, and secretariat for South East Asia Network for Environmental Education (SASEANEE).
Acacia Programme, Uganda.	ICTs for community empowerment with information on agriculture, health, natural resource management, governance, commerce and education.	Content for agricultural and health information to be accessed at three telecentres by rural communities.
NEEDS, Jharkand, India	Food security and livelihoods support (eg grain banking, plant nurseries, micro-finance). Education and health information.	Rural technology park to promote rural industry and support farming using ICTs (eg for pest identification), micro-enterprises.
African Leadership Forum, Nigeria	ICT awareness raising through computer rebuilding and use in schools and youth clubs.	Donated computers 'rebuilt' by recipients to help demystify the technology with the help of professional technicians.
e-Barangay Project, Philippines.	e-government services through a consortium of government agencies, NGOs, private institutions, schools and IT groups.	Computers with internet connections and telephone lines installed in Barangays with online training and access to services such as e-Health.
Self Employed Women's Association (SEWA), Ahmedabad, India	Training for women through the SEWA Academy such as literacy, learning by doing, income generation and problem solving.	Sanchar communication unit operates as documentation centre for reports, surveys and videos, photos and magazines. Women are trained to make video productions on their own issues to mobilise other members and government policy makers.

Development through access to network resources (D.Net), Bangladesh	ICT policy and advocacy, research and dissemination, e-government, networking for capacity building through knowledge sharing among the poor.	Networks for research, business information, rural livelihood information and heritage information using databases and websites.
HELP Resources, Inc. Papua New Guinea	Media training for local youth and community telecentres.	Rural telecentres used by vanilla farmers to access new markets for their crops, arrange orders and shipping documentation.
Social Strategic Foundation, Malaysia	Community mobilisation amongst urban poor to encourage computer literacy and job matching..	Youths trained in ICTs with courses both for those in school and out of school.
Bangladesh Frienship Education Society Bangladesh	Education for all, especially in rural areas, rural development, human rights.	ICT education in village
PROTÉGÉ QV Cameroon	Environmental protection Natural resource management Quality of life.	Setting up cyberspace and library
Digital Divid Data Cambodia	Jobs and educational opportunities for disadvantaged and marginalized people.	Outsourcing data services for business and government

fundamental aspect of the experience that relates to the shared approaches to supporting livelihoods. The NGOs and others taking part in the South-South exchange workshop all aim to serve their respective stakeholders in ways that ultimately impact on their livelihoods and ICTs are being used as enablers in the process. MSSRF has developed a model of using ICTs as an enabler for development through a long-term and flexible approach that puts community ownership at the centre of the knowledge sharing activities. In sharing this approach with MSSRF the NGOs are not just learning about the technological capacity made available in Indian villages but the wider NGO concern of empowering communities through innovative means. In this way the South-South exchange approach can help to reduce unnecessary focus on ICTs as a means to an end in themselves and encourage NGOs to learn from each other to harness them as tools for achieving their existing and long standing goals.

3. New developments and Future prospects

To build on the experience in Pondicherry MSSRF has established a National Virtual Academy for Food Security and Rural Prosperity (NVA) to promote learning at the village level. Outstanding local experts such as the volunteers in the knowledge centres will be selected as fellows of the academy to formalise their role as knowledge brokers within the community. The NVA will provide a basis for co-ordinating further capacity building efforts within the communities and retain the emphasis on local ownership and local content creation. A National Alliance has been formed to promote Mission 2007 that aims to make 'Every Village a Knowledge Centre' by the 60th anniversary of India's independence on 15th August 2007. This will entail establishing more than a hundred thousand knowledge centres to cater to over 630,000 villages and a partnership of over 90 organisations from public, private and non-governmental sectors has been created to take this initiative forward. At Thiruvaiyaru this partnership approach showed initial high-profile results with the inauguration of a village centre with a live telemedicine diagnosis of a patient through a satellite connection⁵ between five remote locations including the Prime Minister's residence in New Delhi. At this event South-South exchange partners were able to witness history in the making and be part of the national news on their first visit to India. More important though is that participants were inspired by the creativity and ambition of MSSRF and the heights to which an NGO can aim for on behalf of the grassroots communities it has chosen to serve; literally into space with the satellite link and figuratively to the holder of the highest political office in the country, the Prime Minister.

References:

- ¹ A report based on the South-South Exchange Travelling Workshop, 15-22 October 2004, sponsored by the Global Knowledge Partnership (GKP).
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- ³ Ashley, C. and Carney, D. (1999) *Sustainable Livelihoods: Lessons from early experience*. London: Department for International Development.
- ⁴ Funded by the Commonwealth of Learning (COL) and with technical support from MSSRF.
- ⁵ With the Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO).

About the author

Robert Chapman is a research officer at the Overseas Development Institute (ODI) in the Rural Policy and Governance Group and is part of the team managing the Agricultural Research and Extension Network, which is ODI's largest network with over 1000 members in 40 countries. He has undertaken research and consultancy for bilateral and multilateral development agencies on information and communication for development, agricultural research and extension systems and sustainable rural development.

Project sites some of which participants visited

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Workshop Report

Geeta Sharma

Programme Manager, Advocacy, OneWorld South Asia

The M S Swaminathan Research Foundation (MSSRF) based in Chennai, India, organized the third South-South Exchange Travelling Workshop during 15-22 October 2004 in Southern India, with financial and logistic support from GKP.

MSSRF held the first South-South Exchange Travelling Workshop in October 2002, with financial support from Hivos, IICD and IDRC, and the second in October-November 2003 with financial and logistic support from GKP.

Purpose

The workshop concept was based on the premise that mere academic education and training was not good enough for development practitioners. Its aim then was to facilitate the exchange of knowledge and experience between visiting participants from civil societies of developing countries and the village communities engaged in ICT-enabled development in South India. These Village Knowledge Centres, part of MSSRF Information Village Research Project (IVRP), are an initiative aimed at ICT-enabled knowledge delivery to the poor for alleviating poverty.

Indian National Centre for Ocean Information Services of the Department of Ocean Development, has helped them increase their yields.

But it's not just the fishermen or men who are benefiting from the information loop at these knowledge centres. A participatory, bottom-up model that required sensitivity and patience by the project team, led the villagers to themselves assess, decide and even demand information that was of use to them. So in all the village knowledge centres, dynamic information is gathered and disseminated daily. This includes information on government and fisheries schemes, employment opportunities, and even counseling. In other knowledge centres, this extends to information on crops, farm practices, animal husbandry, market prices, education, and health care.

This local content creation and sharing in the villages of Pondicherry provided the basis for the **Open Knowledge Network** (www.openknowledge.net) project implemented by OneWorld International and MSSRF and many other OneWorld partners.

The OKN project seeks to harness and facilitate horizontal knowledge generation and sharing among grassroots communities. The content is created using bottom-up participatory methods involving the communities and disseminated by knowledge workers across states, regions and continents, using Internet and world space radio technology.

The **OKN** has facilitated the creation of a supplement for the local newspaper giving information of daily use for the village communities and a weekly radio programme on traditional knowledge, which is being broadcast on the state radio once a week.

The newspaper (Namma Oor Seithi or our Village News) has become a popular source of information on jobs,

and the smooth functioning of the knowledge centres. In Veerampattinam, as many as six volunteers, who have been associated with the KC since its inception, continue to volunteer their services.

The centres also impart computer training to students and local youth. The nominal fee charged for this was the only monetary incentive for the volunteers. But the gains from this centre to the community were big enough to encourage community ownership.

But more than the money, as the participants learnt during their interactions with the volunteers, it was the benefits that accrued to them as families and village communities that made them devote considerable amount of their time to running the centres.

The participants were inspired when they heard that the initiative for some of the centres such as **Sevenakkarianpatti** where dalit women had set up a paper manufacturing plant and the knowledge centre at **Kalitheerthalkuppam**, a milk production village, came from the local communities.

4. Pathways to a development *Antyodaya (unto the last)*

The local ownership model, in which the communities own and manage knowledge centres, did not just bring information that helped improve lives of the village communities. Quietly and sometimes pro-actively, it also opened doors to social change in which women (discussed in Genderpreneurship section) and the Dalits (traditionally marginalized groups based on caste stratifications) got mainstreamed.

The guiding philosophy here was the Gandhian concept of **Antyodaya (unto the last)**. All the knowledge centres, housed in community owned, public buildings are accessible to all irrespective of gender, caste, educational status or class affiliations.

This Antyodaya concept unfolded at two levels. One where the Dalits and other marginalized groups were able to go to these centres for information and even work as volunteers in these Knowledge Centres and gain acceptability in the community.

A dalit woman labourer demanded her rightful wage of Rs 60 as against Rs 40 being

to her was a learning that could be used in any situation, in any context in countries grappling with poverty and false divides.

5. 'Genderpreneurship'

The knowledge centres also showcased how technology used appropriately could empower women. In many of the knowledge centres, women were at the helm as volunteers, knowledge workers, information gatherers and disseminators, managers and as beneficiaries. Not just that, these women, were able to use the information to bring larger benefits to their communities and not just to themselves. In most of the centres, the women at the helm are sourcing information, providing computer education, forming Self Help Groups (SHGs) and are using the loans to educate their children and start cottage industries.

The **Embalam Knowledge Centre**, opened in 1999 in a village temple, is fully managed by women who have been recognized as neutral players above the caste and political machinations that plagued the centre in its initial days.

Two of them, Usha Rani and Kasturi, have won recognition for their social commitment as Fellows of the National Virtual Academy, an initiative of MSSRF to honour and train grassroots knowledge workers.

Today, these women, who had only basic level of education and no computer training, are facilitating computer courses and even running family counseling centres in the evening. They are also using the SHG accounting software developed by MSSRF, and are helping women from neighbouring villages set up such SHGs.

Handling computers and computing and

in setting up of the centre without any monetary incentive, “ This inspiration to others to set up such centres is incentive enough.”

Women of **K. Ramanathapuram** village in Dindigul district provided one of the most inspiring examples of *genderpreneurship*. Some women who had a chance meeting with a MSSRF worker in a seeds cooperative meeting, showed initiative in setting up their own micro-enterprise. Twelve of them formed a self help group, raised the money for two of them to take training from the Department of Plant Pathology of the State Agricultural University, arranged by MSSRF, and set up an enterprise to produce a bio-pesticide – *Pseudomonas fluorescence* – to control seed-borne pathogens. Their product is not just a success but is now being marketed to local farmers, and companies in Chennai and other districts. These women, who have only elementary education, have also developed a five-year business plan.

In a nearby village called **Sevenakkarianpatti**, a group of dalit women have set up another SHG, named after Jhansi Rani, the legendary Indian warrior queen, to produce hand-made paper products from banana waste. Here again, it was the knowledge centre enabled information and handholding support by MSSRF that helped them take a loan, travel hundreds of kilometers to another state to get the relevant training and set up the small scale paper mill. The women are using the ICT facilities offered by the nearby knowledge centre to market their produce. They have even opened an email account to handle the product related queries. These women have come a long way from working as casual labour at Rs 25 a day and that too for only 120 days of the year. They have now repaid most of their loans taken with MSSRF’s help. They too have a business plan and put their earnings back in business. The only money they take home is for their sustenance of their families. And the rates they claim for their labour is a pittance – Rs 30 (two-third of a dollar) a day!

The biopesticide production, at K. Ramanathapuram, started much later than the paper production at Sevenakkarianpatti, but is already a profitable venture. Creating a market

over 100,000 poor in India every year. In a novel scheme, fees charged from 30 per cent of the patients help subsidize or provide free eye care to the rest of the 70 per cent.

To ensure that its free services reach the unreached the hospital has tied up training programmes with NGOs such as MSSRF and DHAN foundation to take eye care to the rural communities. These NGOs test members of the local communities and transmit case reports and photographs of eyes by email or through video conferencing to the doctors at Aravind. Those needing surgeries are brought to the hospitals by village volunteers.

Dr V, whose fingers were crippled by rheumatoid arthritis when he was 45, trained himself to hold the scalpel and perform cataract surgery. In time, he successfully performed thousands of eye surgeries. His story and simple message: *"If you believe that you can, it is already done"* inspired one and all.

Summing up, Valedictory and Certificate Distribution

This final day of the workshop was at the MSSRF headquarters in Chennai. The participants discussed and shared their learning and experiences in small working groups. This was followed by a Plenary where certificates were distributed to the participants.

South-South learning and sharing

The interactive sessions between the development experts and the grassroots level workers at the end of each site visit allowed for the experts to share their learning from the grassroots communities. Also it gave the village communities a chance to learn from experiences in other countries.

Visitors First

Here are some comments by the participants about what they were taking home

and ICTs can be helpful tools and should be used only when necessary and effective.”

For **Frederick Kintu, Project Officer, National Acacia Programme, Uganda**, it was good to understand the concept of knowledge centres was borne from the minds of the rural dwellers themselves. The knowledge centres which are similar to Rural Telecentres in some parts of Uganda and other developing countries have proved to be of paramount importance to both the natives of the villages and to the local govt. for channelising useful information to the local people. “However, the MSSRF should try to position the knowledge centres in a way that the direct support and assistance can be got from the government as well so that the derived costs on service delivery are kept at the minimum and to reduce bureaucratic tendencies in government circles.”

For **Siyam Siwe Sylvie, Coordinator, PROTÉGÉ QV, Cameroon**, the workshop provided her insights into practical ways of using ICTs to alleviate poverty; new strategies for women participating in development processes (with them and not for them); the attitude that giving the skills to the poor through ICTs to change their lives improves their confidence and permits to go faster in the resolution of their problems and that technology is accessible to everyone, it is just a matter of using the most appropriate one.

For **Fernandez Cecilia, New Technologies Program Specialist, ITDG, Peru**, the learning was that technology and services in the knowledge centres had been adapted to the needs of the people; a volunteer network had been built to support the system and it was from the community and that there was a happy blend of old and new technologies and traditional knowledge was given its due importance and was being used and shared.

For **Joshua Kofi Mangesi, Coordinator, Ghana Information Network for Knowledge**, “ the focus of the knowledge centre was not on all the fancy computer equipments, but more on how the communities were improving their livelihoods using the power placed in their own hands the power of information; to innovate, and take charge of their own destinies.”

For **Murari Choudhary, Executive Director, NEEDS, Jharkhand, India**, the workshop provided insights to improve his organization’s ICT interventions in livelihood

and governance spheres “The workshop has helped me in the following two ways – in improving the intervention model and analyzing the issue of our plan on ‘hardware settings’ for block hub and village knowledge centres.”

And then the hosts...

For the village communities and the volunteers and the torchbearers of the ICT led knowledge revolution the questions to the visiting developing experts veered more on their country experiences. Suggestions to improve the already working model were provided. For SHGs for instance it was recommended that they upgrade their data management skills and also opt for eco-tourism to exploit wider markets for their micro-enterprises. Those involved in organic farming, for instance, could tap the growing market for organic foods. The village head of Koonichampet village asked about the land ownership and farming patterns in other countries and was pleasantly surprised to learn that women had the ownership rights in countries such as Ghana and Cameroon. Participants from India offered to share with the village communities, best practices in similar enterprises and SHGs in their areas.

Suggestions for Change

The participants made some suggestions on the workshop format:

- More time should be given for interaction with the communities.
- A folder of all presentations (in English) presented to the delegates in advance can help save time for interaction with the communities.
- Not just successes but failures and challenges should also be shared and discussed.
- A short presentation of Indian culture, people and history on the first day
- Less time for Travelling and more for exchange between participations after visits

- A short feedback session should be held every morning before starting for project sites.
- Every day of the workshop, two or three participants can make presentation on their organisations for better sharing and interactions.

In a nutshell

“There are a number of small groups and institutions around the world actively working in the field of ICT-enabled development and poverty reduction. Why not bring them together and take them to different communities where some good ICT-enabled development work is taking place for exchanging their knowledge and experience among themselves as well as learning from the insights of the local communities that the group will be visiting,” said Prof. Arun, who conceived the idea for such a South-South exchange and worked to make it a reality. The third of such workshops with support from GKP has largely achieved its objective of bringing about such learning by sharing.

For all those involved in the interactive learning, being there (on site) seeing it all, absorbing the learnings and the lessons and then putting them into practice, in relevant situations, is a format worth continuing and improving. Certainly, the exchanges in real world settings is likely to be more productive than the exchanges and sharing on the subject that is taking place in conference halls across the world.

About the author

Geetha Sharma is programme manager, advocacy, OneWorld South Asia, New Delhi. She also runs the New Delhi office of the National Alliance for Mission 2007: Every Village a Knowledge Centre.

